

Scaling up to a more ecological (and reproducible) cognitive neuroscience

Samuel A. Nastase
Princeton Neuroscience Institute
March 3, 2020

 @samnastase

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Uri Hasson

Ken Norman

Talk outline

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

- a brief history of “ecological validity” and the tension between experimental control and ecological generalizability
- perspectives from machine learning, ecological psychology, and evolutionary biology

***Narratives*: fMRI data for evaluating models of naturalistic language comprehension**

- 300+ subjects participating in 800+ scans comprising 20+ spoken story stimuli for 5+ hours of unique stimuli and 6+ days of fMRI data
- how *you* can start using Narratives *today!* (づ_づ)

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

Confronted with the complexity of brain and behavior, neuroscientists traditionally design controlled experiments to reduce the dimensionality of the problem to a few intuitive factors.

Meehl, *Psychol Rep*, 1990

Rozenblit & Keil, *Cogn Sci*, 2002

Jolly & Chang, *Topics Cogn Sci*, 2019

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

Models developed under tightly-controlled experimental manipulations are typically tested in more naturalistic, ecological contexts...

...but results have been mixed

Reinagel, *Curr Opin Neurobiol*, 2001
Simoncelli et al., *Annu Rev Neurosci*, 2001
Bartels & Zeki, *Hum Brain Mapp*, 2004
David et al., *Nature*, 2004
Hasson et al., *Science*, 2004
Kayser et al., *Curr Opin Neurobiol*, 2004
Felsen & Dan, *Nat Neurosci*, 2005
Spiers & Maguire, *Trends Cogn Sci*, 2007
Haxby et al., *Neuron*, 2011
Hasson & Honey, *NeuroImage*, 2012
Maguire, *NeuroImage*, 2012
Hamilton & Huth, *Lang Cogn Neurosci*, 2018
Haxby, Nastase et al., *NeuroImage*, 2020

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

Models developed under tightly-controlled experimental manipulations are typically tested in more naturalistic, ecological contexts...

...but results have been mixed

“We can rightfully claim to understand only 10% to 20% of how V1 actually operates under normal conditions.”

Olshausen & Field, *Neural Comput*, 2005

- biased sampling in neural measurement
- biased sampling of stimuli and tasks
- bias toward simple, interpretable theories
- interdependence of neural variables and context
- publication bias

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

Models developed under tightly-controlled experimental manipulations are typically tested in more naturalistic, ecological contexts...

...but results have been mixed

“We can rightfully claim to understand only 10% to 20% of how V1 actually operates under normal conditions.”

Olshausen & Field, *Neural Comput*, 2005

“In order to behave like scientists, [experimental psychologists] must construct situations in which our subjects are totally controlled, manipulated and measured. We must cut our subjects down to size. We construct situations in which they can behave as little like human beings as possible and we do this in order to allow ourselves to make statements about the nature of their humanity.”

Bannister, *Bull Br Psychol Soc*, 1966

A brief history of “ecological validity”

“Ecological validity”—coined by Egon Brunswik in 1947

Egon Brunswik

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...to mean something else (\neg _ \neg)

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Representative design

- psychology maintains a “double standard” in the application of sampling theory
- subjects are sampled with the goal of generalizing to the population, whereas stimuli and tasks generally are not
- ecological generalizability demands a “representative sampling of situations” where “situational instances in an ecology are analogous to individuals in a population”

Brunswik, *Psychol Rev*, 1943

Brunswik, *Psychol Rev*, 1955

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Nastase, S. A., Goldstein, A., & Hasson, U. (2020). Keep it real: rethinking the primacy of experimental control in cognitive neuroscience. *NeuroImage*, 222, 117254.

The “direct fit” model of biological learning

Relinquishing control—machine learning

Modern artificial neural networks leverage millions of noisy, real-world samples to achieve shockingly good performance at a variety of “cognitive” tasks...

—**but why do neuroscientists find this so unsatisfying?**

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Statistical Science
2001, Vol. 16, No. 3, 199–231

Statistical Modeling: The Two Cultures

Leo Breiman

Choosing Prediction Over Explanation in Psychology: Lessons From Machine Learning

Tal Yarkoni and Jacob Westfall
University of Texas at Austin

Perspectives on Psychological Science
2017, Vol. 12(G) 1100–1122
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sagepub.com/journalsPermissions.nav
DOI: 10.1177/1745691617693393
www.psychologicalscience.org/PPS

Predictive models avoid excessive reductionism in cognitive neuroimaging

Gaël Varoquaux^{1,2} and Russell A Poldrack²

Current Opinion in
Neurobiology

Statistical Science
2010, Vol. 25, No. 3, 289–310
DOI: 10.1214/10-ST5330
© Institute of Mathematical Statistics, 2010

To Explain or to Predict?

Galit Shmueli

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—**but why do neuroscientists find this so unsatisfying?**

The “black box” argument

Artificial neural networks provide an input–output mapping with no explanation of their internal workings. We have simply duplicated the original problem by creating one more black box.

Ashby, 1956

McCloskey, *Psychol Sci*, 1991

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...because we didn’t find what we were looking for

Neuroscientists find this unsatisfying because we **assume** that to perform “cognitive” tasks, a neural network must learn concise, human-interpretable rules about the world.

The “direct fit” model of biological learning

Ecological psychology and “direct perception”

—organisms “directly” perceive opportunities for **adaptive behavior** encoded in the environment—or “affordances”

—all biological learning systems are “embodied” and locked in a continuous organism–environment feedback loop

James J. Gibson

The “direct fit” model of biological learning

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Has this neural network “learned” the sine function?

The model may *appear* to learn the sine function (in the interpolation zone), but this is an incidental byproduct of the input and the fitting procedure.

We can interrogate the model for “representations” of the sine function, but these only exist because we injected them into the training data.

The “direct fit” model of biological learning

Parallels between evolution and direct-fit learning

- evolution relies on “blind” optimization to produce complex organisms adapted to an ecological niche
- evolution relies on local interpolation to capitalize on “affordances” of the environment

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Parallels between evolution and direct-fit learning

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“There is grandeur in this view of life...”

Both evolution and direct-fit learning models produce solutions that may be mistakenly interpreted in terms of elegant design principles, but in fact reflect the interdigitation of “mindless” optimization processes and the structure of the world.

Darwin, 1859
Dawkins, 1986
Dennett, 1995, 2017

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Hasson, U., Nastase, S. A., & Goldstein, A. (2020). Direct fit to nature: an evolutionary perspective on biological and artificial neural networks. *Neuron*, 105(3), 416–434.

Where now for the cognitive neuroscientist?

Where now for the cognitive neuroscientist?

Who knows! ...but here's what I'm working on:

Building large-scale naturalistic neuroimaging datasets to serve as community benchmarks for comparing models of cognition:

- **The *Narratives* collection** of open fMRI story-listening datasets for evaluating models of language comprehension.
- **The *Conversations* dataset** [WIP!] of 24/7 ECoG and audio recorded over hundred of hours of everyday conversations.

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Developing methods for harmonizing diverse datasets and measuring shared representation across individual brains (e.g. **connectivity-based shared response model**).

Nastase, S. A., Liu, Y. F., Hillman, H., Norman, K. A., & Hasson, U. (2020). Leveraging shared connectivity to aggregate heterogeneous datasets into a common response space. *NeuroImage*, 217, 116865.

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High-performing artificial neural networks as models of **context and prediction in natural language**, as well as **competition and cooperation in complex gameplay** [WIP!].

Goldstein, A., Zada, Z., Buchnik, E., Schain, M., Price, A., Aubrey, B., Nastase, S. A., ... & Hasson, U. (2020). Thinking ahead: prediction in context as a keystone of language in humans and machines. *bioRxiv*.

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The neurobiological basis of natural language and communication

The problem of language

- language is uniquely human, limiting the use of nonhuman animal models
- the dynamic and contextual nature of language is unamenable to experimental design

The neurobiological basis of natural language and communication

The dominant experimental paradigm

- controlled experimental tasks and manipulations targeting particular linguistic phenomena
- models derived from small, manufactured datasets are difficult to synthesize

OPINION

The cortical organization of speech processing

Gregory Hickok and David Poeppel

Review

A review and synthesis of the first 20 years of PET and fMRI studies of heard speech, spoken language and reading

Cathy J. Price

Cerebral Cortex December 2009;19:2767-2796
doi:10.1093/cercor/bhp055
Advance Access publication March 27, 2009

FEATURE ARTICLE

Where Is the Semantic System? A Critical Review and Meta-Analysis of 120 Functional Neuroimaging Studies

Jeffrey R. Binder, Rutvik H. Desai, William W. Graves and Lisa L. Conant

Language Imaging Laboratory, Department of Neurology, Medical College of Wisconsin, Milwaukee, WI 53226, USA

Physiol Rev 91: 1357–1392, 2011
doi:10.1152/physrev.00006.2011

THE BRAIN BASIS OF LANGUAGE PROCESSING: FROM STRUCTURE TO FUNCTION

Angela D. Friederici

The neurobiological basis of natural language and communication

The revolution in natural language processing

- neural network models have dramatically transformed natural language processing
- these models are very complex and require very large-volumes of real-world data

BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding

Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, Kristina Toutanova

XLNet: Generalized Autoregressive Pretraining for Language Understanding

Zhilin Yang, Zihang Dai, Yiming Yang, Jaime Carbonell, Ruslan Salakhutdinov, Quoc V. Le

RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach

Yinhan Liu, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, Veselin Stoyanov

Language Models are Few-Shot Learners

Tom B. Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, Pranav Shyam, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, Sandhini Agarwal, Ariel Herbert-Voss, Gretchen Krueger, Tom Henighan, Rewon Child, Aditya Ramesh, Daniel M. Ziegler, Jeffrey Wu, Clemens Winter, Christopher Hesse, Mark Chen, Eric Sigler, Mateusz Litwin, Scott Gray, Benjamin Chess, Jack Clark, Christopher Berner, Sam McCandlish, Alec Radford, Ilya Sutskever, Dario Amodei

The neurobiological basis of natural language and communication

Our goal:

Create a large-scale open neuroimaging dataset that will allow researchers to evaluate and compare neurobiological models of natural language comprehension across diverse spoken narratives.

Narratives

fMRI data for evaluating models of naturalistic language comprehension

uploaded by Sam Nastase on 2019-12-10 - about 1 year ago

last modified on 2021-01-13 - about 1 month ago

authored by Samuel A. Nastase, Yun-Fei Liu, Hanna Hillman, Asieh Zadbood, Liat Hasenfratz, Neggin Keshavarzian, Janice Chen, Christopher J. Honey, Yaara Yeshurun, Mor Regev, Mai Nguyen, Claire H. C. Chang, Christopher Baldassano, Olga Lositsky, Erez Simony, Michael A. Chow, Yuan Chang Leong, Paula P. Brooks, Emily Micciche, Gina Choe, Ariel Goldstein, Tamara Vanderwal, Yaroslav O. Halchenko, Kenneth A. Norman, Uri Hasson

📄 115 👁 18036

OpenNEURO ds002345

<https://openneuro.org/datasets/ds002345>

<http://datasets.datalad.org/?dir=/labs/hasson/narratives>

The *Narratives* data collection

Sharing the “long tail” of neuroscience data

- public, well-curated datasets accelerate research
- re-use of publicly available fMRI datasets saves billions USD in public funding

The “richness” of natural language data

- naturalistic paradigms such as story-listening can accommodate many hypotheses, increasing the re-use value

Ferguson et al., *Nat Neurosci*, 2014

Milham et al., *Nat Commun*, 2018

DuPre et al., *NeuroImage*, 2019

Willems, Nastase et al., *Trends Neurosci*, 2020

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345 unique subjects (ages 18–53 years, mean age 22.2 ± 5.1 years, 204 reported female) participating in **891 functional scans**.

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27 spoken story stimuli ranging from ~3 minutes to ~56 minutes (mean ≈ 12 minutes) for a total of **~4.6 hours of unique stimuli**.

The *Narratives* data collection

Story	Duration	TRs	Words	Subjects
“Pie Man”	07:02	282	957	82
“Tunnel Under the World”	25:34	1,023	3,435	23
“Lucy”	09:02	362	1,607	16
“Pretty Mouth and Green My Eyes”	11:16	451	1,970	40
“Milky Way”	06:44	270	1,058	53
“Slumlord”	15:03	602	2,715	18
“Reach for the Stars One Small Step at a Time”	13:45	550	2,629	18
“It’s Not the Fall That Gets You”	09:07	365	1,601	56
“Merlin”	14:46	591	2,245	36
“Sherlock”	17:32	702	2,681	36
“Schema”	23:12	928	3,788	31
“Shapes”	06:45	270	910	59
“The 21st Year”	55:38	2,226	8,267	25
“Pie Man (PNI)”	06:40	267	992	40
“Running from the Bronx (PNI)”	08:56	358	1,379	40
“I Knew You Were Black”	13:20	534	1,544	40
“The Man Who Forgot Ray Bradbury”	13:57	558	2,135	40
Total:	4.6 hours	11,149 TRs	42,989 words	

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	Total: 4.6 hours	11,149 TRs	42,989 words	
	Total across subjects: 6.4 days	369,496 TRs	1,399,655 words	

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Story stimuli are shared with accompanying word- and phoneme-level **time-stamped transcripts** via Gentle forced alignment.

The *Narratives* data collection

“Pie Man” by Jim O’Grady

I began my illustrious career in journalism in the Bronx where I toiled as a hard-boiled reporter for the Ram, the student newspaper at Fordham University. And one day I’m walking toward the campus center and out comes the elusive Dean McGowan, architect of a policy to replace Fordham’s **traditionally** working- to middle-class students with wealthier, more prestigious ones. T R A H D I H S H A H N A H L I Y So I whip out my notebook and I go up to him and I say, “Dean McGowan, is it true that Fordham University plans to raise tuition substantially above the inflation rate, and if so, wouldn’t that be a betrayal of its mission?” And he stops and looks at me and he says, “Listen up, punk.” And right then, there’s a blur in the corner of my eye which becomes this figure holding a cream pie which becomes the guy standing next to me mashing a cream pie into Dean McGowan’s face. And then runs away. And the Dean is covered with cream. So I give him a moment, and then I say, “Dean McGowan, would you care to comment on this latest attack?” And the Dean says, “Yes, I would care to comment. Fuck you.” So I race back to the newsroom with my scoop and I find the editor, Jim Dwyer,

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MRI data are standardized according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (**BIDS**) and the full provenance is tracked using **DataLad**.

CHANGES	sub-038	sub-083	sub-128	sub-173	sub-218	sub-263	sub-308
README	sub-039	sub-084	sub-129	sub-174	sub-219	sub-264	sub-309
code	sub-040	sub-085	sub-130	sub-175	sub-220	sub-265	sub-310
dataset_description.json	sub-041	sub-086	sub-131	sub-176	sub-221	sub-266	sub-311
derivatives	sub-042	sub-087	sub-132	sub-177	sub-222	sub-267	sub-312
participants.json	sub-043	sub-088	sub-133	sub-178	sub-223	sub-268	sub-313
participants.tsv	sub-044	sub-089	sub-134	sub-179	sub-224	sub-269	sub-314
stimuli	sub-045	sub-090	sub-135	sub-180	sub-225	sub-270	sub-315
sub-001	sub-046	sub-091	sub-136	sub-181	sub-226	sub-271	sub-316
sub-002	sub-047	sub-092	sub-137	sub-182	sub-227	sub-272	sub-317
sub-003	sub-048	sub-093	sub-138	sub-183	sub-228	sub-273	sub-318
sub-004	sub-049	sub-094	sub-139	sub-184	sub-229	sub-274	sub-319
sub-005	sub-050	sub-095	sub-140	sub-185	sub-230	sub-275	sub-320
sub-006	sub-051	sub-096	sub-141	sub-186	sub-231	sub-276	sub-321
sub-007	sub-052	sub-097	sub-142	sub-187	sub-232	sub-277	sub-322
sub-008	sub-053	sub-098	sub-143	sub-188	sub-233	sub-278	sub-323
sub-009	sub-054	sub-099	sub-144	sub-189	sub-234	sub-279	sub-324
sub-010	sub-055	sub-100	sub-145	sub-190	sub-235	sub-280	sub-325
sub-011	sub-056	sub-101	sub-146	sub-191	sub-236	sub-281	sub-326
sub-012	sub-057	sub-102	sub-147	sub-192	sub-237	sub-282	sub-327
sub-013	sub-058	sub-103	sub-148	sub-193	sub-238	sub-283	sub-328
sub-014	sub-059	sub-104	sub-149	sub-194	sub-239	sub-284	sub-329
sub-015	sub-060	sub-105	sub-150	sub-195	sub-240	sub-285	sub-330
sub-016	sub-061	sub-106	sub-151	sub-196	sub-241	sub-286	sub-331
sub-017	sub-062	sub-107	sub-152	sub-197	sub-242	sub-287	sub-332
sub-018	sub-063	sub-108	sub-153	sub-198	sub-243	sub-288	sub-333
sub-019	sub-064	sub-109	sub-154	sub-199	sub-244	sub-289	sub-334
sub-020	sub-065	sub-110	sub-155	sub-200	sub-245	sub-290	sub-335
sub-021	sub-066	sub-111	sub-156	sub-201	sub-246	sub-291	sub-336
sub-022	sub-067	sub-112	sub-157	sub-202	sub-247	sub-292	sub-337
sub-023	sub-068	sub-113	sub-158	sub-203	sub-248	sub-293	sub-338
sub-024	sub-069	sub-114	sub-159	sub-204	sub-249	sub-294	sub-339
sub-025	sub-070	sub-115	sub-160	sub-205	sub-250	sub-295	sub-340
sub-026	sub-071	sub-116	sub-161	sub-206	sub-251	sub-296	sub-341
sub-027	sub-072	sub-117	sub-162	sub-207	sub-252	sub-297	sub-342
sub-028	sub-073	sub-118	sub-163	sub-208	sub-253	sub-298	sub-343
sub-029	sub-074	sub-119	sub-164	sub-209	sub-254	sub-299	sub-344
sub-030	sub-075	sub-120	sub-165	sub-210	sub-255	sub-300	sub-345
sub-031	sub-076	sub-121	sub-166	sub-211	sub-256	sub-301	
sub-032	sub-077	sub-122	sub-167	sub-212	sub-257	sub-302	
sub-033	sub-078	sub-123	sub-168	sub-213	sub-258	sub-303	
sub-034	sub-079	sub-124	sub-169	sub-214	sub-259	sub-304	
sub-035	sub-080	sub-125	sub-170	sub-215	sub-260	sub-305	
sub-036	sub-081	sub-126	sub-171	sub-216	sub-261	sub-306	
sub-037	sub-082	sub-127	sub-172	sub-217	sub-262	sub-307	

CHANGES	sub-038	sub-083	sub-128	sub-173	sub-218	sub-263	sub-308
README	sub-039	sub-084	sub-129	sub-174	sub-219	sub-264	sub-309
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sub-008	sub-053	sub-098	sub-143	sub-188	sub-233	sub-278	sub-323
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sub-025	sub-070	sub-115	sub-160	sub-205	sub-250	sub-295	sub-340
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sub-030	sub-075	sub-120	sub-165	sub-210	sub-255	sub-300	sub-345
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sub-032	sub-077	sub-122	sub-167	sub-212	sub-257	sub-302	
sub-033	sub-078	sub-123	sub-168	sub-213	sub-258	sub-303	
sub-034	sub-079	sub-124	sub-169	sub-214	sub-259	sub-304	
sub-035	sub-080	sub-125	sub-170	sub-215	sub-260	sub-305	
sub-036	sub-081	sub-126	sub-171	sub-216	sub-261	sub-306	
sub-037	sub-082	sub-127	sub-172	sub-217	sub-262	sub-307	

The *Narratives* data collection

345 unique subjects (ages 18–53 years, mean age 22.2 ± 5.1 years, 204 reported female) participating in **891 functional scans**.

27 spoken story stimuli ranging from ~3 minutes to ~56 minutes (mean ≈ 12 minutes) for a total of **~4.6 hours of unique stimuli**.

Story stimuli are shared with accompanying word- and phoneme-level **time-stamped transcripts** via Gentle forced alignment.

MRI data are standardized according to the Brain Imaging Data Structure (**BIDS**) and the full provenance is tracked using **DataLad**.

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<https://github.com/snastase/narratives>
<http://datalad.org> — discover
<http://github.com/datalad/datalad> — contribute
<http://handbook.datalad.org> — learn

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Evaluating the *Narratives* collection

Quality control

- automated quality control using MRIQC
- head motion, spatial smoothness, and tSNR

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Early auditory cortex
Glasser et al., *Nature*, 2016

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The *Narratives* data collection

An invitation to all “research parasites”

— evaluate your favorite language model across 300+ subjects and 20+ stories

— compare processing pipelines for naturalistic story-listening data

— event segmentation, functional alignment, functional network estimation, etc...

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Where now for the cognitive neuroscientist?

Toward a more ecological cognitive neuroscience

Ecological considerations must play a central role in both model development and model evaluation to avoid confining ourselves to a “self-created ivory tower ecology”

In the context of **representative design**, the “challenge of further [isolating variables] must be met by after-the-fact, mathematical means”

Brunswik, 1955

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In the context of **representative design**, the “challenge of further [isolating variables] must be met by after-the-fact, mathematical means”

—**late commitment**: relax theoretical assumptions during design and data collection; formalize hypotheses as models for evaluation at the analysis stage

Kriegeskorte et al., *Front Syst Neurosci*, 2008

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— **system identification**: evaluate and compare models according to *out-of-sample prediction* performance under naturalistic conditions

Wu et al., *Annu Rev Neurosci*, 2006

Naselaris et al., *NeuroImage*, 2010

Nunez-Elizalde et al., *NeuroImage*, 2019

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DuPre et al., *NeuroImage*, 2020

Willems, Nastase et al., *Trends Neurosci*, 2020

Nastase et al., *NeuroImage*, 2020

Rocca & Yarkoni, *PsyArXiv*, 2020

Thanks!

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Feilong Ma
J. Swaroop Guntupalli
Andrew C. Connolly
Cara E. Van Uden
Rebecca Philip

Kenneth A. Norman
Elizabeth A. McDevitt
Anne C. Mennen
Paula P. Brooks

Brain Imaging Analysis Kit—BrainIAK
<https://brainiak.org>

Princeton Handbook for Reproducible Neuroimaging
<https://brainhack-princeton.github.io/handbook>

**National Institute
of Mental Health**

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Connectivity SRM

We first split each story into a training (first half) and test (second half) sets.

onset	word
0.2	so
0.7	I
1.8	was
2.3	a
2.4	junior
⋮	
404.0	well
404.3	I
404.5	said
406.0	nope
409.6	my

onset	word
0.6	this
1.0	is
1.1	a
1.2	story
2.2	that
⋮	
418.6	they
418.8	would
419.0	have
419.1	to
419.2	talk

I Knew You Were Black, by Carol Daniel:

"So I was a junior in college when I got my first paying job in my field on the radio. This is not an internship, I'm getting a check..."

"...Well I said, nope. My father speaks this way, my mother speaks this way, and they're from Mississippi. My siblings all speak this way, God-given talent; no training, no classes, none of that, just little old me."

The Man Who Forgot Ray Bradbury, by Neil Gaiman:

"This is a story that I wrote called *The Man Who Forgot Ray Bradbury*, and I wrote it as a birthday present for Ray on his 91st birthday. It begins like this..."

"...They would have to talk about the man who wrote 'to be or not to be'. No, not the film starring Jack Benny whose real name was Benjamin Kubelsky, who was raised in Waukegan, Illinois, an hour or so outside Chicago."

Connectivity SRM

We first split each story into a training (first half) and test (second half) sets.

Intersubject functional connectivity (ISFC) computed from training data based on 360-area multimodal cortical parcellation.

Simony et al., *Nat Commun*, 2016
 Glasser et al., *Nature*, 2016

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The shared response model (**SRM**) factorizes the group data into subject-specific topographic transformations and a single shared connectivity space across datasets and stimuli.

Chen et al., *NeurIPS*, 2015

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Topographic transformations used to project response time series from the test set into shared space.

Time-segment classification

cSRM improves between-subject time-segment classification

- 10-TR (15-second) response trajectories
- between-subject correlation-based classifier

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Evaluating cSRM

Three ways to evaluate functional alignment

- between-subject time-segment classification
- intersubject correlation analysis
- semantic forward encoding model

Regions of interest

- early auditory cortex (EAC)
- auditory association cortex (AAC)
- temporo-parieto-occipital junction (TPOJ)
- posterior medial cortex (PMC)

Time-segment classification

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- 10-TR (15-second) response trajectories
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Intersubject correlation

cSRM improves intersubject time-series correlations

- increases number of *orthogonal* features with $r > .10$
- increases the dimensionality of shared information across subjects

Semantic encoding model

cSRM improves forward encoding

- word2vec semantic embeddings
- between-subject encoding model

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- word2vec semantic embeddings
- between-subject encoding model
- increases the dimensionality of shared **semantic** information across subjects

Estimating a shared response space across heterogeneous naturalistic story-listening datasets

Key intuitions

- coarse, whole-brain connectivity signatures can be used to “bootstrap” fine-grained alignment
- transformations derived from connectivity can align spatiotemporal response trajectories
- story-listening “task” may yield commensurate connectivity patterns across diverse stimuli

Projecting subject data into shared space improves between-subject correlation, classification, and encoding.

Connectivity SRM also dramatically increases the dimensionality of shared information across subjects.

This improvement generalizes to subjects and stories excluded when estimating the shared space.